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CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MOTOR TRANSPORT SERVICES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the current state of road transport services, their role in the development of the economy and society, and modern development trends. The study considers digitalization, electronic logistics platforms, GPS monitoring, the introduction of ecological vehicles and "smart transport" technologies as priority areas for the development of the sector. It also covers issues related to improving the quality of services, modernization of transport infrastructure, and the development of international transport corridors.

Key words: globalization, urbanization, digital economy, international logistics, integration, motor transport services, Uzbekistan - 2030 strategy, industry, agriculture, construction, trade, services.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется текущее состояние автомобильного транспорта, его роль в развитии экономики и общества, а также современные тенденции развития. В качестве приоритетных направлений развития сектора рассматриваются цифровизация, электронные логистические платформы, GPS-мониторинг, внедрение экологичных транспортных средств и технологий «умного транспорта». Также рассматриваются вопросы повышения качества услуг, модернизации транспортной инфраструктуры и развития международных транспортных коридоров.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, урбанизация, цифровая экономика, международная логистика, интеграция, автомобильный транспорт, стратегия Узбекистана до 2030 года, промышленность, сельское хозяйство, строительство, торговля, услуги.

INTRODUCTION

Today, road transport services are of strategic importance for all sectors of the economy and society, playing an important role in ensuring the mobility of the population, effectively organizing cargo and passenger transportation, strengthening interregional economic ties, and integrating into the international logistics system. Especially in an era of globalization, urbanization, and the development of the digital economy, the need for road transport services is increasing.

The main tasks of the road transport system are defined in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the transport sector. In particular, according to the Law "On Road Transport", the main tasks of road transport are to meet the needs of the population and the economy with high-quality transport services, to ensure the safe transportation of passengers and cargo, to develop transport infrastructure, and to ensure environmental safety. These tasks fully meet today's requirements, since economic growth and the expansion of entrepreneurial activity are increasing the demand for transport services.

The need for road transport services is manifested, first of all, in the sustainable development of the country's economy. Industry, agriculture, construction, trade and service sectors depend on the prompt delivery of products. Therefore, freight transport services increase logistics efficiency and reduce production costs. Passenger transport services, on the other hand, ensure the free movement of the population to work, education and medical institutions, and serve social stability.

This issue is also closely related to the goals of the Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy. The Strategy identifies the modernization of transport infrastructure, the creation of modern logistics centers, the development of international transport corridors, the widespread introduction of environmentally friendly vehicles, and the development of digital transport services as priority tasks. These areas are aimed at improving the quality of motor transport services and creating a convenient transport system for the population.

In particular, the formation of an environmentally friendly transport system based on the principles of a "green economy" is one of the important directions of the strategy. In this regard, the use of electric cars, gas-powered vehicles, and buses that meet modern environmental standards is gaining importance. This will help reduce air pollution and ensure the environmental safety of the population.

Digitalization processes are also increasing the importance of road transport services. Online taxi services, electronic logistics platforms, GPS monitoring systems, and electronic payment services are making the transport system more convenient and transparent. This is in line with the principles of "Digital Uzbekistan" and the tasks of digitizing public services set out in the Strategy of Uzbekistan-2030.

Today, road transport services have become an important factor in economic development, population well-being and territorial integration. Their development is of great importance in implementing the tasks set out in the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan and achieving the goals of the Strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030. Therefore, modernization of transport infrastructure, improvement of service quality and development of an ecological and digital transport system are among the urgent tasks of today.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Analysis of local and foreign literature sources on this topic, Peter Drucker, Michael Porter, Donald Bowersox, David Simchi-Levi, Martin Christopher, Philip Kotler, Frederick Taylor, Henry Ford, Joseph Juran, W. Edwards Deming, John Mentzer, Douglas Lambert, Paul Krugman, Alfred Marshall and Gary Becker have studied the issues of efficiency, logistics, management and economic efficiency of transport services, while local economists such as Qudratilla Abdurahmonov, Bakhodir Khodiev, Shavkat Ayupov, Saidakhror G'ulomov, Mukhtor Ikromov, Abdug'ani Abduvaliyev, Akmal Saidov, Botir Usmonov, Sherzod Mustafakulov, Nodir Jumayev, Ilhom Mahkamov are conducting scientific research on the efficiency of road transport services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The scientific research used statistical and economic analysis methods, analysis, synthesis, abstract-logical analysis, as well as selective observation, sociological survey, SWOT analysis, and comparative methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Today, road transport services in Uzbekistan are developing rapidly as one of the most important sectors of the economy. The increase in passenger and freight traffic in the country, urbanization processes, the expansion of e-commerce and the logistics system are further increasing the need for road transport services. In particular, significant changes are observed in intercity travel, public transport, taxi services, and international freight routes.

Currently, the state is implementing large-scale reforms to modernize transport infrastructure, build new highways, renew bus fleets, and develop digital transport services. In particular, the Ministry of Transport is paying special attention to increasing passenger safety, introducing electronic payment systems, and establishing modern logistics centers. At the same time, the digitization of transport services, increasing the number of environmentally friendly vehicles, and developing international transport corridors are among the priority tasks within the framework of the Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy.

It is important to implement a number of measures to improve road transport services. First of all, it is necessary to modernize the transport infrastructure and improve the quality of interregional highways. By increasing the number of modern buses and environmentally friendly electric vehicles, it is possible to ensure the quality of passenger transportation and environmental safety. Also, the development of logistics centers and «intelligent transport systems» will reduce freight costs and help effectively manage traffic flows.

Expanding digitalization processes is also an important direction. Online monitoring, GPS control, electronic ticketing and mobile payment systems increase the transparency of services and create convenience for the population. At the same time, it is necessary to train qualified personnel in transport enterprises, increase the professional culture of drivers and improve service standards (Table 1).

Table 1. The volume of motor transport services provided in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023-2025 (in billion soums)

No.	Region name	2023	2024	2025
1	Republic of Uzbekistan	57906.7	73439	95853.8
2	Republic of Karakalpakstan	1787.2	2432.5	3160.1
3	Andijan region	4709.6	6120.3	7739.5
4	Bukhara region	4213.7	5296.9	6930.4
5	Jizzakh region	1596.7	2100.3	2503.9
6	Kashkadarya region	4436.9	5281.3	6886.8
7	Navoi region	1888.6	2372.5	2964.4
8	Namangan region	3404.6	4330	5731
9	Samarkand region	7095.8	8996.8	11431.4
10	Surkhandarya region	2379.9	2874.4	3673.8
11	Syrdarya region	793.8	1060.7	1362.3
12	Tashkent region	7545.1	9544.8	12274.9
13	Fergana region	5493	6936.2	9836.5
14	Khorezm region	3083.3	4033.5	5109
15	Tashkent city	9476.8	12053.9	16245.4

This table reflects the dynamics of growth in the volume of road transport services by regions of Uzbekistan in 2023–2025. Analysis of the table shows that the volume of transport services in all regions of the republic is increasing year by year. This indicates that the transport and logistics system in the country is developing, economic activity is increasing, and the demand for freight and passenger transportation is increasing.

In 2023, the volume of services in the republic amounted to 57,906.7 billion soums, in 2024 this figure reached 73,439 billion soums, and in 2025 - 95,853.8 billion soums. Thus, the total growth over three years is about 65%. This is explained by the reforms being implemented in the transport sector, improving infrastructure, and expanding logistics services.

The highest indicator among regions is the city of Tashkent. The indicator, which was 9,476.8 billion soums in 2023, reached 16,245.4 billion soums in 2025. This indicates high economic activity in the capital, the service sector, and the population's need for transport. Tashkent region and Samarkand region also showed high growth rates. In Tashkent region, the indicator increased from 7,545.1 billion soums to 12,274.9 billion soums, and in Samarkand region - from 7,095.8 billion soums to 11,431.4 billion soums.

Fergana region, Andijan region, and Kashkadarya region are also among the leading regions in terms of the volume of transport services. In particular, in Fergana region, the figure will reach 9,836.5 billion soums by 2025, due to the dense concentration of industry, trade, and population in the region.

The lowest indicators are observed in Syrdarya region, Jizzakh region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. For example, in Syrdarya region, the indicator, which was 793.8 billion soums in 2023, amounted to 1,362.3 billion soums in 2025. This is explained by the lower economic and demographic potential in these regions compared to other regions.

Another important aspect that can be seen from the data in the table is that there is a steady growth trend in all regions. In particular, the growth rate accelerated further between 2024 and 2025. This indicates that the country is modernizing its transport infrastructure, creating new logistics centers, and developing digital transport services.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The research shows that the market for road transport services in Uzbekistan is developing rapidly. In the future, the introduction of modern logistics systems, the expansion of the use of environmentally friendly vehicles, the improvement of interregional roads, and the acceleration of digitalization processes will be of great importance to further increase the efficiency of transport services.

As a result of the research and analysis conducted, the following proposals were developed:

- Mobile applications should be created that allow passengers to see the location of a bus or taxi in real time. This will reduce waiting times and improve service quality;
- Old buses and minibuses should be replaced with modern, comfortable and environmentally friendly vehicles. Air conditioning, Wi-Fi and electronic payment systems will create convenience for passengers;

- Regular training for drivers, attention to traffic rules and etiquette should be organized. This will increase safety and customer satisfaction.

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